

Usability Guidelines for Arab E-Government Websites

Authors : Omya Alosaimi, Asma Alsumait

Abstract : The website developer and designer should follow usability guidelines to provide a user-friendly interface. Many guidelines and heuristics have been developed by previous studies to help both the developer and designer in this task, but E-government websites are special cases that require specialized guidelines. This paper introduces a set of eighteen guidelines for evaluating the usability of e-government websites in general and Arabic e-government websites specifically, along with a check list of how to apply them. The validity and effectiveness of these guidelines were evaluated against a variety of user characteristics. The results indicated that the proposed set of guidelines can be used to identify qualitative similarities and differences with user testing and that the new set is best suited for evaluating general and e-governmental usability.

Keywords : e-government, human computer interaction, usability evaluation, usability guidelines

Conference Title : ICCCISE 2014 : International Conference on Computer, Communication and Information Sciences, and Engineering

Conference Location : Paris, France

Conference Dates : December 30-31, 2014